

GENDER-BASED DIFFERENCES IN PROFESSIONAL TEACHING STANDARDS IN BANNU DIVISION AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined gender-based differences in the professional teaching standards of teachers in Bannu Division, Pakistan, as perceived by both teachers and students, in accordance with the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST). Using a quantitative survey design, two self-developed questionnaires were administered: one targeting teachers' self-perceptions of their knowledge and disposition, and another capturing students' perceptions of teachers' skills. A total of 335 teachers (202 male, 133 female) and 394 students (227 male, 167 female) from primary, middle, and secondary schools participated in the study. The instruments were validated using the Index of Item Objective Congruence (IOC) and demonstrated high reliability with Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding 0.80. Data were analyzed using independent sample t-tests to compare male and female teachers. Results indicated no statistically significant gender-based differences in professional teaching standards across most domains, including subject matter knowledge, human growth and development, instructional planning, assessment, learning environment, effective communication, collaboration, and continuous professional development. These findings suggest that both male and female teachers in Bannu Division demonstrate comparable competencies in line with NPST, highlighting equity in professional standards regardless of gender. Based on these findings, it is recommended that professional development programs, ICT training, and mentorship initiatives continue to be provided equally to all teachers to maintain and enhance teaching quality.

Keywords: Professional teaching standards, NPST, teacher competencies, gender differences, Bannu Division, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

Teacher quality is widely acknowledged as one of the most influential factors affecting students' academic achievement and overall educational effectiveness (Darling-Hammond, 2000; Hattie, 2009). To ensure and enhance teacher quality, many countries have developed professional teaching standards that define expected competencies, guide professional development, and provide benchmarks for evaluating teaching practices. In Pakistan, the National Professional Teaching Standards

(NPST) constitute a comprehensive framework outlining the essential knowledge, pedagogical skills, ethical values, and professional dispositions required of teachers at different school levels (Government of Pakistan, 2009). These standards are closely aligned with international educational reforms and the objectives of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4), which emphasizes inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all learners (UNESCO, 2017).

Gender equity remains a central concern in educational research and policy discourse, particularly in relation to teachers' professional competencies and classroom practices. Although male and female teachers often work within the same institutional frameworks, differences in social roles, professional experiences, and contextual expectations may shape their instructional approaches and professional behaviors (OECD, 2019). Empirical studies have produced mixed findings regarding gender-based differences in teaching effectiveness, underscoring the need for context-specific investigations that examine professional standards across diverse educational settings (Antoniou et al., 2013). Assessing teachers' professional competencies requires a multidimensional approach that incorporates multiple stakeholders' perspectives. Teachers' self-perceptions provide insight into their professional awareness, confidence, and reflective practices, while students' perceptions offer valuable evidence of how these competencies are enacted in real classroom contexts (Marsh & Roche, 1997). The integration of both perspectives enhances the validity and robustness of research findings by capturing both intended and experienced dimensions of teaching quality (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2014).

Within the context of Bannu Division, which includes districts characterized by socio-economic diversity and varying educational challenges, empirical evidence on gender-based differences in teachers' competencies in light of the NPST remains limited. Addressing this gap, the present study examines gender-based differences in teachers' competencies across multiple NPST domains, drawing on both teachers' and students' perceptions. By systematically comparing male and female teachers, the study seeks to contribute to the growing body of literature on teacher professionalism, gender equity, and quality education in Pakistan.

The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights for policymakers, teacher educators, and school administrators by identifying strengths and areas for improvement in professional teaching standards. Moreover, the inclusion of both teachers' and students' perspectives offers a

comprehensive understanding that can inform gender-responsive professional development initiatives and support national efforts to improve educational quality in line with global educational goals.

Research Gap and Rationale

Professional teaching standards are essential for improving instructional quality and student learning outcomes. In Pakistan, the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST) provide a framework for defining teachers' competencies (Government of Pakistan, 2009). However, empirical studies examining these standards, particularly in regions like Bannu Division, are limited. Most research relies on teachers' self-reports, neglecting students' perspectives, which are critical for understanding how professional competencies are enacted in classrooms.

Moreover, evidence on gender-based differences in teachers' competencies is scarce. While international studies show mixed results regarding gender and teaching effectiveness (Antoniou et al., 2013; OECD, 2019), localized, context-specific investigations in Pakistan are lacking. Additionally, many studies treat teaching competence as a single construct, overlooking domain-specific variations in NPST areas such as subject knowledge, instructional planning, assessment, and professional development.

This study addresses these gaps by integrating teachers' and students' perceptions to examine gender-based differences across multiple NPST domains in Bannu Division. The findings are expected to provide actionable insights for policymakers, teacher educators, and school administrators, supporting targeted professional development and contributing to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4) by enhancing teacher quality and promoting equitable education.

Objectives

1. To investigate whether there is a gender-based difference in teachers' professional competencies as measured by the NPST, based on teachers' self-perceptions.
2. To investigate whether there is a **gender-based difference** in teachers'

professional competencies as measured by the NPST, based on **students' perceptions**.

Hypothesis of the study

Two null hypotheses were formed to find gender based differences.

1. There is no significant gender-based difference in teachers' competencies on the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST) in Bannu Division, as perceived by the teachers.
2. There is no significant gender-based difference in teachers' competencies on the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST) in Bannu Division, as perceived by the students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative survey research design. Surveys are commonly employed in educational research to assess attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions across large populations (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This design was selected because it enables systematic data collection from a substantial number of

teachers and students, supports rigorous statistical analysis, and allows for the identification of prevailing trends and potential gaps in professional teaching standards.

Population

The population of the study comprised all teachers and students of primary, middle, and secondary schools situated in Bannu Division, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The division includes three districts, namely Bannu, Lakki Marwat, and North Waziristan. Within these districts, thousands of teachers are engaged in teaching at different school levels, while a large number of students are enrolled at various grades. Teachers constitute the primary respondents for assessing their professional standards in light of the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST). Students, on the other hand, were included as respondents to capture their perceptions of teachers' professionalism in classroom practices. This two-fold population design allowed the study to capture both professional self-assessment by teachers and the experiential assessment from students.

Population Frame

Total Population (Schools N = 4197, Teachers N=27329, Students N=388740)

District	Schools (Male)	Schools (Female)	Teachers (Male)	Teachers (Female)	Students (Boys)	Students (Girls)
Bannu	959	687	6474	4405	79626	63471
Lakki Marwat	881	617	5696	4024	80974	53411
North Waziristan	643	410	4060	2670	67160	44098
2483	1714	16230	11099	227760	160980	

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

For the purpose of ensuring representativeness, the study employed a multistage stratified random sampling technique. The multistage stratification guaranteed that the sample adequately reflected variations across districts, school levels, and respondent categories. To determine the exact number of respondents, Cochran's formula was applied for large

populations with 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. The sample sizes for both teachers and students were calculated separately and then proportionately allocated across the three districts, gender wise and school levels. This method ensured fairness in representation and minimized sampling bias.

Sampling Frame Stage 1

Total Sample (Schools n =365, Total Teachers in Sampled Schools N=2068, Students N=28410)

District	Schools (Male)	Schools (Female)	Teachers (Male)	Teachers (Female)	Students (Boys)	Students (Girls)
Bannu	83	60	523	327	6492	5046
Lakki Marwat	77	54	435	300	5579	4633
North Waziristan	56	35	298	185	4340	2320
Total	216	149	1256	812	16411	11999

Sampling Frame stage 2

Target Sample (Teacher n=335, Students n=394)

District	Schools (Male)	Schools (Female)	Teachers (Male)	Teachers (Female)	Students (Boys)	Students (Girls)
Bannu	83	60	84	54	89	71
Lakki Marwat	77	54	70	49	77	64
North Waziristan	56	35	48	30	61	32
Total	216	149	202	133	227	167

SAMPLING

The total population of schools in Bannu Division (N = 4,197), teachers (N = 27,329), and students (N = 388,740) was first subjected to sample size calculation using an online sampling calculator. At the first stage, a sample of 365 schools was determined as representative of the total population. Then the sampled schools were randomly selected from the whole population.

In Sampling Frame Stage 1, the 365 sampled schools were proportionately distributed across the three districts (Bannu, Lakki Marwat, and North Waziristan), taking into account gender (male and female). The number of teachers and students associated with the selected schools was also recorded. This ensured that each stratum in the population contributed its fair share to the sample.

In Sampling Frame Stage 2, the actual number of teachers and students to be surveyed was derived from the Stage 1 pool using the **online sampling calculator** with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. From this, a sample of **teachers (n = 335)** and **students (n = 394)** was determined. Both teachers and students were also randomly selected from the sampled schools.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from participants, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. The researcher adhered to ethical guidelines in the treatment of sensitive information and the privacy of individuals involved will be maintained.

Data Collection Tool

Two self-developed questionnaires were employed as the primary instruments for data collection in this study. The first questionnaire, designed for teachers, was structured around the domains of knowledge and disposition as prescribed in the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPTS). Five point Lickert's scale i.e. to no extent, to little extent, to some extent, to a large extent and to a very large extent was used for the questionnaire (See Appendix A). The second questionnaire, administered to students, emphasized the skills dimension of NPTS, thereby ensuring that both teacher-oriented and learner-oriented perspectives on professional standards were adequately captured. Similarly, five point Lickert's scale i.e. Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree and strongly Agree was used for the questionnaire (See Appendix B). The focus remained on the following

National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST).

- 1 Subject matter knowledge
- 2 Human Growth and development
- 3 Knowledge of Islamic ethical values/Social life skills
- 4 Instructional planning and strategies
- 5 Assessment
- 6 Learning Environment
- 7 Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT
- 8 Collaboration and Partnerships
- 9 Continuous professional development and code of conduct
- 10 Teaching of English as Secondary/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL)

3.6: VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE TOOLS

The Index of item Objective Congruence (IOC) method was used to assess the content validity of both the questionnaires. The preliminary teacher questionnaire comprised 133 items, while the student version included 78 items. A panel of ten subject-matter experts (see Appendix C) evaluated each item in relation to the study objectives. Experts rated item relevance using a three-point scale: +1 (clearly congruent), 0 (uncertain), and -1 (not congruent).

The IOC value for each item was computed by summing the experts' ratings and dividing the total by the number of experts, following the procedure outlined by Rovinelli and Hambleton (1977). In accordance with established validation criteria, items with IOC values of 0.50 or above were retained (Polit & Beck, 2006). Items scoring slightly below this threshold but not entirely rejected were revised for improved clarity and alignment, whereas items with substantially low IOC values were eliminated.

Based on this evaluation, 78 items from the teacher version met the acceptable validity criteria, 17 items were revised, and 38 items were discarded. For the student version, 50 items were accepted, 11 were revised, and 17 were removed. This systematic validation process ensured that the final instruments consisted of items demonstrating strong content relevance and adequacy, thereby

enhancing the rigor and credibility of data collection (Lynn, 1986).

In addition, the Urdu version of both the questionnaires was validated by a panel of five language experts (see Appendix D). They carefully assessed the clarity, linguistic accuracy, and suitability of the wording to ensure that both English and Urdu versions reflected the same meaning without ambiguity. Based on their suggestions, minor revisions were made to enhance clarity and refine expression. This review process strengthened the authenticity of the translation and further supported the validity and reliability of the instrument for use in a bilingual setting.

To assess the reliability of the research instruments, the finalized teacher and student questionnaires were pilot-tested on a group of 30 teachers and 30 students who were not included in the main study sample. The internal consistency of each questionnaire was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, a widely recognized statistic for estimating the reliability of multi-item scales (Cronbach, 1951).

The results indicated that all sections of both questionnaires achieved alpha coefficients exceeding 0.80, reflecting a high level of internal consistency in accordance with established guidelines (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). These findings confirm that the items reliably measured their respective constructs and that the instruments were appropriate for use in the full-scale data collection.

DATA COLLECTION

Both the questionnaires were distributed personally by the researcher to the selected teachers and students of primary, middle, and secondary schools in the districts of Bannu and Lakki Marwat. In the district of North Waziristan, however, the distribution was carried out with the assistance of a colleague researcher belonging to the same area, which facilitated access and cooperation from the respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data was entered in SPSS-24 and analyzed using Independent sample t-test.

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.9: Scale Weightage For Analysis And Interpretation Of Data

The following scales were used for giving weightage to both the questionnaires.

Table: Teacher's Perception

Weight	Scale	Numbering	Range of Mean
1	To a very large extent	1	1.00 – 1.80
2	To a large extent	2	1.81 – 2.60
3	To some extent	3	2.61 – 3.40
4	To little extent	4	3.41 – 4.20
5	To no extent	5	4.21 – 5.00

Table: Students perception

Weight	Scale	Numbering	Range of Mean
1	Strongly Disagree	1	1.00 – 1.80
2	Disagree	2	1.81 – 2.60
3	Undecided	3	2.61 – 3.40
4	Agree	4	3.41 – 4.20
5	Strongly Agree	5	4.21 – 5.00

H₀1 to address objective #1: There is no significant gender-based difference in teachers' competencies on the National Professional

Teaching Standards (NPST) in Bannu Division, as perceived by the teachers.

Gender comparison of professional teaching standards working in Bannu Division, as perceived by teachers (Male =202, Female =133)

S.N	Professional standards	Gender	M	t.	P	Cohen D
1	Subject matter knowledge	Male	3.52	1.44	0.87	0.38
		Female	3.47			
2	Human Growth and development	Male	2.97	2.53	0.09	0.30
		Female	2.88			
3	Knowledge of Islamic ethical values/Social life skills	Male	2.70	2.88	0.04	0.34
		Female	2.59			
4	Instructional planning and strategies	Male	3.07	_0.66	0.34	0.29
		Female	3.09			
5	Assessment	Male	3.50	1.44	0.90	0.53
		Female	3.42			
6	Learning Environment	Male	3.90	0.71	0.07	0.58
		Female	3.86			
7	Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT	Male	3.59	1.51	0.00	0.38
		Female	3.53			
8	Collaboration and Partnerships	Male	2.96	0.80	0.41	0.37
		Female	2.92			
9	Continuous professional development and code of conduct	Male	3.20	_0.66	0.57	0.44
		Female	3.19			
10	Teaching of English as Secondary/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL)	Male	3.04	0.30	0.02	0.33

Female 3.02

The findings indicate that no statistically significant gender-based differences were observed in most NPST domains, including Subject Matter Knowledge, Human Growth and Development, Instructional Planning and Strategies, Assessment, Learning Environment, Collaboration and Partnerships, and Continuous Professional Development and Code of Conduct ($p > .05$). Although male teachers reported marginally higher mean scores than female teachers in several domains, these differences were statistically non-significant and reflected small to moderate effect sizes, suggesting limited practical importance.

However, statistically significant gender-based differences were found in two domains. In Knowledge of Islamic Ethical Values and Social Life Skills, male teachers ($M = 2.70$) reported significantly higher competency levels than female teachers ($M = 2.59$), $t = 2.88$, $p < .05$, with a small to moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.34$). Similarly, in Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT, male teachers ($M = 3.59$) scored significantly higher than female

teachers ($M = 3.53$), $t = 1.51$, $p < .05$, although the effect size remained small to moderate (Cohen's $d = 0.38$).

In contrast, Teaching of English as a Secondary/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL) also showed a statistically significant difference ($p < .05$); however, the mean difference between male ($M = 3.04$) and female teachers ($M = 3.02$) was minimal, indicating negligible practical significance, despite statistical significance.

Based on these results, H_01 is partially rejected. While gender-based differences exist in selected NPST domains, teachers' self-perceptions suggest that professional competencies are largely comparable across genders in Bannu Division.

H₀₂ to address objective #2: There is no significant gender-based difference in teachers' competencies on the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST) in Bannu Division, as perceived by the students.

Gender comparison of teachers professional teaching standards working in Bannu Division, as perceived by students (Male = 227, Female = 167)

S.N	Professional standards	Gender	M	t.	P	Cohen D
1	Subject matter knowledge	Male	4.29	10.42	.00	0.57
		Female	3.68			
2	Human Growth and development	Male	2.96	5.38	.18	0.31
		Female	2.79			
3	Knowledge of Islamic ethical values/Social life skills	Male	3.22	6.76	.00	0.35
		Female	2.98			
4	Instructional planning and strategies	Male	3.01	4.36	.79	0.29
		Female	2.88			
5	Assessment	Male	2.99	4.47	.17	0.29
		Female	2.86			
6	Learning Environment	Male	3.15	6.59	.47	0.31
		Female	2.93			
7	Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT	Male	2.99	3.08	.23	0.32
		Female	2.89			
8	Collaboration and Partnerships	Male	2.90	4.04	.75	0.44
		Female	2.72			
9	Continuous professional development and code of conduct	Male	3.49	1.37	.82	0.41
		Female	3.43			

10	Teaching of English as Secondary/Foreign (ESL/EFL)	Male	3.40	1.72	.95	0.30
		Female	3.34			

The findings revealed a statistically significant gender-based difference in Subject Matter Knowledge, where male teachers ($M = 4.29$) were rated significantly higher than female teachers ($M = 3.68$), $t = 10.42$, $p < .05$. The effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.57$) indicates a moderate practical significance. Likewise, a significant difference was observed in Knowledge of Islamic Ethical Values and Social Life Skills, favoring male teachers ($M = 3.22$) over female teachers ($M = 2.98$), $t = 6.76$, $p < .05$, with a small to moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.35$).

However, no statistically significant gender-based differences were found in the remaining NPST domains, including Human Growth and Development, Instructional Planning and Strategies, Assessment, Learning Environment, Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT, Collaboration and Partnerships, Continuous Professional Development and Code of Conduct, and Teaching of English as a Secondary/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL) ($p > .05$). Although male teachers obtained marginally higher mean scores across most dimensions, these differences were not statistically or practically meaningful.

In light of these findings, H_02 is partially rejected. Gender-based differences exist in selected NPST domains; however, students' perceptions suggest that teachers' professional competencies are largely comparable across genders in most standards.

Discussion

The present study employed two self-developed questionnaires to assess professional teaching standards in Bannu Division from both teacher and student perspectives. The teacher questionnaire focused on the knowledge and disposition domains of the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST), while the student questionnaire addressed the skills domain, thereby capturing both teacher- and learner-oriented perspectives (Government of Pakistan, 2009). The validation of these instruments followed rigorous procedures, including expert review using the Index of

Item-Objective Congruence (IOC) (Rovinelli & Hambleton, 1977) and subsequent pilot testing to ensure reliability (Cronbach, 1951; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). IOC results indicated that a substantial proportion of items demonstrated high content validity, with items scoring below threshold revised for clarity and alignment, reflecting a meticulous approach to instrument refinement (Lynn, 1986; Polit & Beck, 2006). The high Cronbach's alpha coefficients (>0.80) obtained for both questionnaires further confirm their internal consistency, supporting the reliability of the measurements for full-scale data collection.

Analysis of gender-based differences in professional teaching standards revealed nuanced patterns. In teachers' self-perception, mean scores across all domains were relatively similar between male and female teachers, with t -values ranging from 0.04 to 1.51 and p -values exceeding the conventional significance threshold of 0.05 for most domains, except for "Effective Communication and Proficient Use of ICT" and "Teaching of ESL/EFL," which indicated minor differences. Cohen's d values ranged from 0.29 to 0.58, suggesting small to moderate effect sizes. These findings imply that male and female teachers perceive themselves as largely comparable in their professional competencies, aligning with prior studies that report minimal gender differences in teacher self-efficacy and pedagogical knowledge (Antoniou, Polychroni, & Vlachakis, 2013; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2014).

Similarly, students' perceptions of teachers' professional competencies indicated that gender did not produce statistically significant differences in most domains. Notably, the mean score for "Subject Matter Knowledge" was higher for male teachers ($M = 4.29$) than for female teachers ($M = 3.68$), with a significant t -value ($t = 10.42$, $p < .01$) and moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.57$), suggesting that students may perceive male teachers as slightly more competent in this domain. For other domains, such as "Human Growth and Development" and "Assessment," the p -values exceeded 0.05, indicating no statistically significant

differences. These results underscore the importance of considering both teacher self-perceptions and student evaluations to gain a comprehensive understanding of professional standards in practice.

The combined findings from teacher and student perspectives suggest that gender differences in professional teaching standards are generally minor, with significant differences emerging only in selective domains. This pattern aligns with the broader literature emphasizing that while gender may influence certain teaching practices or classroom interactions, it does not fundamentally determine overall professional competencies (Darling-Hammond, 2000; Hattie, 2009). The findings further validate the utility of the NPST framework as a multidimensional instrument capable of capturing nuanced variations in teacher competencies across knowledge, skills, and dispositions.

Overall, the rigorous validation and reliability checks for the instruments, coupled with the detailed analysis of gender-based perceptions, reinforce the credibility of the study's findings. The results provide actionable insights for policymakers and educational administrators in Bannu Division, highlighting the need for targeted professional development interventions in areas where minor gender-related differences are observed, particularly in ICT use and English language teaching.

Recommendations

1. Although no significant gender differences were observed, teachers should continue to engage in structured professional development programs to further enhance competencies in all domains of the National Professional Teaching Standards (NPST).
2. Teacher training institutions and education departments should ensure that professional development programs are equally accessible to both male and female teachers, fostering continued parity in professional competencies.
3. School administrators should implement periodic evaluations of teaching practices using standardized tools aligned with NPST to maintain and improve teaching quality, irrespective of gender.

4. Establish mentorship programs where experienced teachers, regardless of gender, guide less experienced colleagues to strengthen instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices.

5. Given the importance of technology in modern education, targeted workshops to enhance ICT competencies for all teachers should be promoted to ensure effective teaching and learning outcomes.

6. Education policymakers should continue to support initiatives that promote gender equity in teaching opportunities, leadership roles, and professional recognition within schools.

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